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ARTICLE

Solid Phase Crystallization of Amorphous Silicon at the Two-Dimensional Limit

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Epitaxy of silicene-on-Ag(111) renewed considerable interest in silicon (Si) when scaled down to the two-dimensional (2D) limit. This remains one of the most explored growth case in the emerging 2D materials fashion beyond graphene. However, out of a strict silicene framework, other allotropic forms of Si still deserve attention for technological purposes. Here, we present 2D Solid Phase Crystallization (SPC) of Si starting from an amorphous-Si on Ag(111) in atomic coverage to gain a crystalline-Si layer by post-growth annealing below 450 °C, namely Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) Back-End-of-Line (BEOL) thermal budget limit. Moreover, taking benefit from the 2D-SPC scheme, we also managed to write crystalline-Si pixels on the amorphous-Si matrix. Our *in situ* and *ex situ* analysis show that an in-plane interface or a lateral heterojunction between amorphous and crystalline-Si is formed. This amorphous-to-crystalline phase transformation suggests that 2D silicon may stem not only from an epitaxially grown layer but also from thermal self-organization/assembly.

Introduction

Miniaturization of 2D silicon (Si) has been instrumental in pushing Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS) based nanoelectronics towards its limit. This scaling is dramatically reflected on the dimensional reduction of the active body channel in devices like transistors.^{1,2} The two major allotropes of ultrathin 2D Si are: diamond-like and graphene-like. The diamond-like Si is the conventionally exploited form even inside the more advanced device architectures (e.g. FinFET³ and multi-bridged nanosheet transistors⁴) and of the frontier mainstream. On the other hand, and as the name implies the graphene-like Si⁵, namely silicene, refers to the newly discovered atomically thin form retaining the hexagonal symmetry. Silicene in short time have rekindled the Si based applications for instance nanoelectronics⁶, optics⁷, energy⁸ etc.. Similarly, 'Xene' refers to the family of graphene-like materials beyond graphene.^{9–12}

Silicene-on-Ag(111)^{13–19} configuration is one of the most explored growth case in the Xenos synthesis, thanks to the Ag(111) substrate commensurability with the monolayer silicene. This growth can be articulated into three categories based on the growth temperature.^{13–19} First is the low temperature growth (~ 100 °C) where the deposition results in amorphous-Si on Ag(111). Second is the medium temperature

regime (~200 °C) where monolayer silicene appears in mixed crystalline phases (named using the superstructure notation): 4x4, $\sqrt{13}\times\sqrt{13}$ R13.9° type-I and II in addition to some other minor reconstructions. Third one is the high temperature growth (~300 °C) where $2\sqrt{3}\times 2\sqrt{3}$ R30° mixes with 4x4. Higher temperatures result in a 2D layer degradation and eventually in desorption. In the last two cases, the appearance of $\sqrt{3}\times\sqrt{3}$ R30° (with respect to the silicene lattice) structures marks the start of second layer and from second layer onwards $\sqrt{3}\times\sqrt{3}$ R30° phase grows on top of the underneath mixed phase.

While amorphous-Si at the 2D level has no structural affinity with silicene, it can be taken as the background to trigger an amorphous-to-crystalline phase transformation. Although to date, it remains untouched in the silicene growth context, it has previously been demonstrated that it is possible to realize amorphous-to-crystalline phase transformation. This is usually referred to as 'Solid Phase Crystallization (SPC)'^{20–25} and is one of the preferred way to synthesize crystalline-Si that are used in solar cell^{26,27} by heating the thick amorphous-Si at an elevated temperature (500–600 °C). Therefore, it could be interesting to realize SPC on even thinner amorphous-Si at 2D level with thickness of few atomic layers.

In this regard, we present the 2D-SPC of amorphous-Si deposited on Ag(111) at low temperatures by Molecular Beam Epitaxy (MBE). First, we will show the phase transformation in a large scale area throughout the sample of ~10x10 mm². Based on *in situ* and *ex situ* monitoring during each process stage, we show that this evolution can be accomplished by heating the sample at 300 °C, namely at a much lower temperature than that used for bulk silicon (~500–600 °C) thanks to the thickness in few atomic layers. In addition, we show that the 2D-SPC can

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be effectively translated/reproduced locally by means of an electron beam (e-beam) irradiation by selectively writing crystalline-Si areas, hereafter termed 'Si pixels', on the 2D amorphous-Si layer. A comprehensive analysis of this in-plane heterojunction, where even silicene fingerprints were hinted, will be discussed in detail.

Experimental

The growth and *in situ* low-energy electron diffraction (LEED)/Auger characterization were carried out in a LAB10 MBE system by ScientaOmicron. A complete sample synthesis comprises three stages: (i) preparation, (ii) growth and (iii) encapsulation. First the commercially available Ag(111) were cut ($\sim 10 \times 10$ mm²) and were loaded inside the MBE system. These Ag(111) wafers were prepared with cycles of 20 mins sputtering with Ar⁺ (1 kV/10 mA) followed with successive annealing at 550 °C for 20 minutes that were first verified with sharp Ag:1x1 LEED spots and then contaminants free with Auger. Following the preparation, Si was deposited at 100 °C from a Si sublimator (SUSI by Dr Eberl MBE Komponenten GmbH). In agreement with previously reported silicene growth calibration^{17,18}, the calibration of the flux was set and assigned as a monolayer (ML) Si which gives 20-25% of Auger attenuation of the main Auger Ag peak if growth was carried out at 225 °C. The growth rate was fixed at 0.03 ML/sec. After observing the amorphous structure of the grown Si layer with LEED, two methodologies were implemented to realize the 2D-SPC. In the first methodology, aiming at large area crystallization, the amorphous-Si samples were heated for 15 minutes at 300 °C on the same MBE manipulator. In the second methodology, aiming for selective area/spot crystallization, crystalline 'Si pixels' were written with high energy electron beams (2.5 keV; 0.5 μ m spot size) using the LEED-Auger filament source. The last step is the deposition of amorphous Al₂O₃ capping layer thereby to allow their *ex situ* investigation. The details of this encapsulation can be found elsewhere²⁸.

Once the samples are unloaded from the MBE system, *ex situ* micro-Raman characterization was performed using a Renishaw InVia spectrometer. The spectrometer is equipped with a 514 nm (2.41 eV) solid state laser and a 50x (0.75 numerical aperture) objective. Similarly, the incident laser power was kept below 1 mW in order to avoid sample damages.

Results

Fig. 1 presents a series of LEED images probing the diffraction pattern evolution as a function of the annealing temperature (Ta). First, sharp diffraction spots from the (1x1) Ag(111) surface are clearly visible post to the substrate preparation (see Fig. 1(a)). After that, there are no LEED patterns in Fig. 1(b) that was taken after deposition of 2 MLs Si at 100 °C, thus confirming the total coverage of Ag(111) substrate with an amorphous structure. The 2 MLs sample was chosen to ensure robustness against many rounds of annealing in this particular case. The amorphous phase continued to appear even when Ta was

increased to 250 °C as shown in Fig. 1(c). However, when the heating was carried out at Ta= 300 °C, the surface is no longer amorphous and additional LEED spots along with the ones from the (1x1) Ag(111) surface appear. This brings evidence of a 2D-SPC at ~ 300 °C. Similarly, when the same sample was further heated to Ta= 350 °C the LEED spot intensity starts to decrease (Fig.1(e)) and it finally vanishes at Ta= 400 °C (Fig. 1f) where the LEED pattern resembles the one in Fig. 1a thereby suggesting a complete Si desorption. The LEED patterns in Fig. 1d and 1e display features typical of the $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ superstructure. As mentioned before, in the context of silicene-on-Ag(111), this suggests the complete wetting of the Ag(111) surface with the first silicene monolayer and at least the second silicene layer in progress (we will refer to this configuration as to Si: $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ in the following). Fig. S1 of Supplementary Information 1 (SI1) compares the Auger spectra acquired post to preparation which further confirms the Si deficiency on the surface when heated at 400 °C. Additionally, we can notice that the thermal budget to realize phase transformation is significantly reduced down to ~ 300 °C with respect to that needed for thicker amorphous-Si (500-600 °C). A possible explanation for this gain in the thermal budget should be the dimension reduction at the start with amorphous-Si which is ultra-thin.

Fig. 1 Series of LEED patterns acquired at various stages. (a) Ag(111) surface after preparation and before Si deposition. (b) after depositing a nominal coverage of 2 monolayers of Si at 100 °C. (c) after annealing the surface in (b) for 15 minutes at 250 °C. (d-f) after 15 minutes long annealing of surface in (b) at 300, 350, and 400 °C, respectively. White circles represent the Ag:1x1 spots. Green and blue are respectively Si integer and $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ spots with respect to integer order Si spot inside green circle. All LEED images are taken at incident energy $E_i = 50$ eV.

Fig. 2 presents three sample coverages: 1, 1.5, and 2 MLs of amorphous-Si achieved by tuning the growth duration at a given flux and temperature. This sample series was considered since we encountered Si desorption with nominal coverage < 1 ML as shown in SI2. After annealing at 300 °C, in the reported LEED patterns, Si: $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ phase dominates in all the cases and the patterns differ by 30° rotation. This observation may suggest that the amount of material have a special role during the phase transformation in determining the majority of rotational domains at equivalent thermal energy provided. For instance,

at low coverage, i.e. 1 ML (Fig. 2(a)), crystalline pattern barely managed to appear. However, when the coverage was increased to 1.5 and 2 MLs (Figs. 2(b-c)), the LEED patterns are sharp, therefore suggesting competition between two processes: desorption vs. crystallization.

Fig. 2(a-c) LEED patterns acquired after depositing 1, 1.5, and 2 monolayer coverage respectively on Ag(111) at 100 °C followed by annealing at 300 °C for 15 minutes. Represented once, black circle is Ag:1x1 spot, green is Si integer order spot and blue is Si: $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ spots with respect to integer order Si spot inside green circle. LEED images (a-c) are taken at incident energy $E_i = 54$ eV. (d-e) the Auger spectra acquired at various stages on sample in c focusing on Si peak at 92 eV and Ag peak at 354 eV respectively in d and e. The three color spectra represent as: black is post to preparation on bare Ag(111) surface, blue is before annealing once amorphous-Si is deposited and pink is post to annealing at 300 °C for 15 minutes.

For the sample with 1.5 MLs, the Auger spectra of Si and Ag are plotted in Figs. 2(d-e), respectively, at different stages of the process. In particular, the black lines are the spectra acquired after the initial substrate preparation, the blue lines are after Si deposition at 100 °C, and the pink lines are the spectra after SPC. It is worth noting that the Auger spectra after Si deposition at 100 °C (blue lines), combined with the absence of a LEED pattern (Fig. 1(b)), suggest the formation of a relatively thicker Si (few MLs) in amorphous form. This is made clear by the main Ag peak that attenuates significantly ($\sim 70\%$ with respect to black spectrum Ag peak) and the sharp appearance of main Si peak at 92 eV. A possible explanation for the observed thick Si deposition is that at low growth temperature the adatoms diffusion length decreases significantly. In addition, the re-evaporation is reduced significantly since adatoms are landing on “cold” surface. However, after crystallization (pink spectrum) the Ag peak attenuation readjusts back to $\sim 35\%$ suggesting the Ag(111) surface should have been wet completely with the first layer and second layer towards the completion, thereby fully confirming a very thin Si layer that is in atomic layers thickness regime. This suggests that at 300 °C the Si adatoms should have undergone thermally induced self-organization. The consequence of this thermal diffusion kinetics

on the surface is the solid phase transformation of amorphous Si into a crystalline-Si sheet as confirmed by the appearance of the LEED pattern (Fig. 2(b)).

The LEED patterns in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show no signs of 4×4 and $\sqrt{13} \times \sqrt{13}$ R13.9° silicene phases. As elaborated in the introduction, these are the dominant silicene phases when silicene is grown directly on Ag(111). In the new growth approach that we report here, the LEED patterns in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, is favouring the $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ Si(111) phases. This connotes the growth process decisive for final crystalline Si phases observed. Indeed, these two processes follow distinct growth kinetics. In the first case, Si adatoms will have sufficient diffusion length thanks to the moderate growth temperature that ensures crystal growth from the beginning.²⁹ In the second case, since the adatoms encounter ‘colder’ surface, the diffusion is limited that even forbids the formation of a crystalline layer, and the deposition takes place in the form of bulk amorphous layer. Thus, the first step in this growth approach is to create a direct contact of a crystalline substrate and an amorphous layer. This is confirmed from Fig. 1 (a & b) where the amorphous Si film (Fig. 1(b)) shadows the Ag:1x1 spots that were previously visible before Si deposition in Fig 1(a). As detailed in the literature by Olson & al.²¹, the crystalline substrate now recasts as a template for the crystallization process of an unordered amorphous film to an ordered crystalline layer upon adequate thermal annealing, and in a layer-by-layer fashion the phase transformation of the crystalline layers takes place. This suggests that for our thicker samples the crystallization process should have undergone from the first layer and then the following layers. The reappearance of Ag(111) spots along with the $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ Si spots post to 2D-SPC strongly points the same.

Fig. 3 presents *ex situ* Raman analysis carried out on same sample series (1, 1.5 and 2 MLs thick) in order to have a complementary insight into the 2D-SPC. Before unloading from the MBE reactor, the samples were capped with non-reactive amorphous Al_2O_3 to avoid silicon oxidation. The Raman spectra (Figs. 3(a-c)) reveal a nearly constant Raman shift and the characteristic Si peak placed at $\sim 521\text{-}522$ cm^{-1} . However, the most crucial observation is that the Si peak neither is asymmetrical nor there are any convincing signs of additional components located at lower wave vectors ($400\text{-}520$ cm^{-1}). As a result, none of the Raman spectra can validate the typical silicene-on-Ag(111) fingerprints^{30,31}. In addition, the observed Si: $\sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{3}$ structure may be reconciled with an induced diffusion of Ag atoms from the substrate as reported on monolayer silicene grown at ~ 200 °C when heated to 300 °C by Solonenko et al.³² In that case, the *in situ* Raman spectroscopy indicated the transformation from silicene to diamond like Si-nanocrystals. If so, the crystallized Si reflects the diamond-like form in 2D regime of ultra-low thickness.

Fig. 3 Raman spectra acquired for three samples corresponding respectively to fig. 2 with (a) red (1 monolayer), (b) green (1.5 monolayers) and (c) blue (2 monolayers). The black spectrum in each subplot is the reference Si for that sample.

Now we turn our attention to spot crystallization where we aim to validate the 2D-SPC by means of a local e-beam exposure instead of the integral heating of the sample. Figs. 4(a-d) presents the LEED patterns acquired immediately after the e-beam exposure on a particular region of the amorphous-Si surface with 1.5 MLs thickness using the same LEED/Auger e-beam source. The beam energy is set constant at 2.5 keV while the four levels of exposure duration: 7, 14, 28, and 56 seconds, were applied on different sites of the sample. First, even with a very short e-beam exposure, i.e. 7 seconds in Fig. 4(a), pale diffraction features appear in the LEED pattern from the diffuse pattern of the amorphous-Si state. Second, both the Ag:1x1 (black circle in Fig. 4(b-d) and Si:√3x√3 R30° (blue and green circle in Fig. 4(b-d)) LEED spots are becoming progressively brighter with increasing the exposure time, and at 28 seconds (Fig 4(c)) the pattern evolves similar to the one obtained in large area crystallization (see Fig. 1(d) for comparison) therein displaying intense and well defined diffraction spots. This suggests that an equivalent thermal budget to that provided by the annealing at 300 °C, should have been generated by the local e-beam exposure thus resulting in a localized crystallization, namely a 'spot 2D-SPC'. Fig. S3 of SI3 presents the LEED images taken along one spot in two in-plane orthogonal directions (lateral and longitudinal) of the sample surface which shows the evolution of LEED patterns. From the LEED images in SI3 it is clear that the LEED patterns start to diminish once we move away from the spot centre and at one point no LEED patterns can be observed at all. Therefore, we can conclude that there is a co-existence of amorphous and crystalline-Si in the same sample surface. In other words, a lateral heterostructure is made by placing amorphous-Si and crystalline -Si on the same substrate, thus realizing crystalline-Si pixels that are embedded in an amorphous-Si matrix by e-beam writing.

In order to facilitate the *ex situ* Raman analysis of the Si pixel, a 'Region of Interest (ROI)' was created in the amorphous sample by several e-beam exposures (5-10 times; 2.5keV for 56 s) (SI4). While doing so, the manipulator was moved slightly in xy plane (assigning z orthogonal to the surface or parallel to the e-beam). Therefore, the crystalline surface is the fusion of several pixels on the amorphous-Si matrix. The reason behind opting this approach is that we were unable to locate even the matrix of pixels on the sample in the *ex situ* environment. This confirms that spot area is much smaller when compared with the nominal one made with manipulator reading. In the

following, we detail the *ex situ* Raman analysis made on this ROI that is inside the amorphous-Si.

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Fig. 4 LEED images showing the spot crystallization which were obtained after exposing the amorphous Si-on-Ag(111) surface with high energy electron beam (2.5 keV). The exposure duration is set as: (a) 7 seconds, (b) 14 seconds, (c) 28 seconds, and (d) 56 seconds. (e) is the plot of nominal crystalline area (mm²) respectively with respect to the e-beam exposure duration (a-d). The nominal Si coverage deposited on Ag(111) was 1.5 monolayers. Black circle Ag:1x1 spots, (represented once) green: integer order Si spots and blue: Si:√3 x √3 spots with respect to the integer order Si spots inside green circle. LEED images (a-d) are taken at incident energy E_i = 54 eV.

Fig. 5 presents the positional Raman spectroscopy carried out on the interface between aforementioned ROI and amorphous-Si. Two regions can be recognized in Fig. 5(a), one characterized by a sharp Si-related peak in magenta, green, blue and red spectra and the other region characterized by a broad spectral band, brown spectrum. The shape profile of this brown spectrum (see SI5 Fig. S5(a) for more spectra) is consistent with that of phonon modes in amorphous materials, in which the interatomic bond length distribution is highly dispersed. From these two observations and for convenience, we arbitrarily assign this interface co-ordinate (D) as origin where D>0 is amorphous region and D<0 belongs to the crystalline region. However, what is most striking is the emergence of an additional peak component that is highly pronounced at the interface region (Fig. 5(a), magenta spectrum at D = -100 μm) as shown with two components Lorentzian-Gaussian fitting (magenta curve in Fig. 5(b)) after the background subtraction which gives the accurate position of the Raman peaks: 521.29 cm⁻¹ and 506.56 cm⁻¹ respectively for principle (dark blue curve in Fig. 5(b)) and secondary peak (orange curve in Fig. 5(b)). SI5 Fig. S5(b) presents additional spectra close to this region which further substantiate this secondary Si peak that makes the spectrum asymmetrical in ~100-200 μm at the junction. To quantitatively assess the relative weight between the principal and secondary peak (referred as major and minor peak in the following, respectively), we deconvolved the Raman spectra with two fitting components after background subtraction.

Fig. 5 Raman analysis of the interface between amorphous-Si and crystalline-Si. (a) As acquired Raman spectra as a function of position. (b) fitted Raman spectrum corresponding to pink spectrum in (a) where gray curve is raw data, pink is the fit result, dark-blue and orange are two used Lorentzian-Gaussian components. (c-d) quantification of spectra in (a) and (b). (c) the intensity of major and minor components with respect to the position. (d) the location of major and minor Si related Raman peaks.

In Fig. 5(c) we plot, as a function of the spatial position, the relative weight of each peak calculated as the ratio, $I_{\text{peak}}/I_{\text{tot}}$, where I_{peak} is the intensity of the (major, minor) peak and I_{tot} is the sum of the peak intensities derived by the fitting procedure. The solid circle and diamond represent major and minor peaks respectively. Fig. 5(d) presents the centre of the two peaks where we can confirm the major Si peak at 521-522 cm⁻¹ and minor one \sim 490-500 cm⁻¹ in all the cases. The emergence of asymmetry with pronounced side peak is further confirmed in Fig. 5(c). For instance, moving from red to magenta spectrum, we can notice that the spectral separation between the major and minor peak (represented respectively with dots and bricks) is reduced.

These findings converge towards a 'silicene-in-junction' in between the crystalline-Si and amorphous-Si that should be in the few atomic layers in terms of thickness. First the black spectrum (S15 Fig. S5(a)) along with no LEED patterns (Fig. 1(b)) and Auger spectra as discussed in Figs. 2(d-e) confirm a thick amorphous region (\sim 6 MLs)¹⁵. Secondly, the red Raman spectrum (Fig. 5) with Si: $\sqrt{3}\times\sqrt{3}$ LEED patterns (Fig. 4) suggests a diamond-like crystalline-Si as seen before with large area crystallization. Furthermore, this red spectrum shares identical Raman spectra features: (i) lacking asymmetry, (ii) almost no

secondary component and (iii) main Si peak located at 521-522 cm⁻¹ which further consolidate this. DOI: 10.1039/D2NA00546H

The major reason for these signatures should be the thermal energy gradient, that ebeam spot creates around its centre, once we move away from the pixel centre. At one point (corresponding to -100 μm or the pink curve in fig. 5), the thermal energy should have been low enough that not only prevented excessive Si desorption but also forbid the complete transformation from a graphene-like to diamond-like phase. This furthermore resulted in the junction thickness between the diamond like crystalline-Si and amorphous Si (S15 Fig. S5(c)). Most importantly, the curve is asymmetrical with a side hump which in the context agrees with the fingerprint of the multilayer silicene on Ag(111).³³

As we already noticed, spot crystallization via 2D-SPC is possible well below < 450 °C thus opening the avenue for low-thermal budget applications of locally crystallized nanoscale Si. Patterning Si spots (pixels) within an amorphous-Si 2D matrix with a low-temperature processing is compliant with the CMOS process flow provided silicene is made rid of the Ag below³⁴. This full CMOS compatibility³⁵ makes spot crystallization suitable for embedding silicene transistors in a pre-patterned CMOS platform with a thermally compliant process scheme. We believe this can be an additional tool for the route towards Gate-All-Around (GAA)³⁶⁻³⁸ silicene field effect transistors (FET)³⁹.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we investigated SPC on amorphous-Si on Ag(111). We demonstrated, with *in situ* LEED/AES and *ex situ* Raman spectroscopy, SPC at 2D level occurs at \sim 300 °C which is well below the CMOS BEOL thermal budget of 450 °C. Similarly, we also described a method to achieve SPC by selective writing 'Si pixels' with e-beam source that can be engineered further by adjusting free parameters. We believe this new growth approach to write 'Si pixels' at the 2D level can be interesting in the future nanomaterials engineering routes by making use of more precise (e.g. focused e-beam⁴⁰ or different (e.g. laser⁴¹) heating printer.

Author Contributions

DSD conceived the idea, planned the growths and *in situ* analysis. EB and CM carried out the *ex situ* Raman acquisitions. DSD wrote the manuscript. CM, CG and AM provided critical feedback on the manuscript. AM supervised the project.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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